

RUSSIAN AGGRESSION AS A THREAT TO THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF EUROPE: THE UKRAINIAN DIMENSION

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Abstract. The article deals with issues related to Russian aggression against Ukraine in the context of the existing threat to sustainable development of Europe. Particular attention is drawn to the treachery of aggressive Russian policy towards not only the Ukrainian people but also the peoples of other countries which are traditionally considered to be the zone of influence and interests of the Kremlin. The authors have concluded that as long as the current Russian political leadership is poised to stay in power, it is impossible to expect any democratic changes in this country. The mentality of war professed by both the Russian authorities and Russian society is in opposition to the existing basic European values and democratic freedoms. At the same time, even the replacement of the current government will not automatically improve the political situation in the country. Only the disintegration of Russia into separate independent states will deprive it of its imperial status. Ukraine is considered not only in terms of the necessary support and assistance from the perspective of the legal and moral foundations of human civilization but also as a likely candidate for an active role in the post-war political configuration of Europe. This conviction, as stated in the article, is based on the significant achievements made by the Ukrainian people in recent years in the context of meeting European standards of life and work in the demonstrated success in protecting national interests, the very idea of the existence of an independent Ukrainian state.

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Formulation of the problem in general. Analysing the recent events related to Russia's aggression against Ukraine a number of issues related to threats to Europe's sustainable development should be highlighted. Aggressive Russian policy threatens not only the Ukrainian people but also the peoples of other countries that are traditionally in the Russian sphere of influence and interests. The mentality of war that pervades both the Russian government and Russian society contradicts basic European values and democratic freedoms, and thus, under the current Russian political leadership there is little hope for democratic changes in Russia. The collapse of the empire as a result of the victory of the Ukrainian people in the current war with the enormous support and comprehensive assistance of Western partners will naturally prevent a threat to the sustainable development of European states, promote democratic changes in other countries and finally create the necessary conditions for Ukraine's political and economic rise in the context of building a sovereign democratic state.

Analysis of recent research and publications. In many contemporary scholarly studies, the problem of the development of Ukrainian statehood is intertwined with the analysis of sustainable development and components of political life, such as the study of the policy of appeasement of the aggressor, Russia's past and present imperial policy and its totalitarian legacy. Among others, we would like to highlight the well-known works by T. Snyder, A. Bezanson, Z. Brzezinski, A. Kappeler, A. Novak, George O. Liber, F. Fukuyama, and others. [Snyder, 2021; Bezanson, 2017; Brzezinski, 2022; Kappeler, 2022; Novak, 2021; Liber, 2019; Fukuyama, 2020].

In order to characterise the main features of the current situation, the research focuses on the analysis of Russian hostility that has developed historically, its accentuated impact on the Ukrainian nation and European political reality and the gradual political "awakening" of the Ukrainian people [Brzezinski, 2022: p.18]. In particular, T. Snyder, drawing attention to the categorical denial by the Russian authorities of the possibility of the Ukrainians having an independent nation, writes that "in the last quarter of the nineteenth century the idea that Russia was a single nation and all Eastern Slavs were Russians became dominant" [Snyder, 2021: p.154]. The attitude of the Western political elite to the Russian state is somewhat explained by A. Bezanson's words about the fascination with Russia and fear of it, attempts to let it into their world and attempts to expel it from there which failed [Bezanson, 2017: p.5]

Studies by Ukrainian scholars such as S. Plokyh, E. Magda, I. Rushchenko and others deserve considerable attention. The researchers are of the opinion that Russian aggression against Ukraine not only threatens the security and territorial integrity of Ukraine but also has a broader impact on European stability and threats to the sustainable development of Europe and the world. Thus, E. Magda emphasizes that "Russia seeks to subjugate the 'model democracies', to push the united Europe off the political map of the world, depriving it of the status of one of the centres of influence in order to take its place and strengthen its positions" [Magda, 2017: p.215]. The Ukrainian people themselves became one of the main targets of imperial policy their mental characteristics which are manifested not only through hostilities but also through an unleashed hybrid war.

Special mention should be made to the scientific works prepared by scholars in the context of the full-scale Russian aggression against Ukraine. It is worth paying attention to the collective monograph "Ukrainian Society in the Context of War" (S. Dembitskyi, O. Zlobina, N. Kostenko and others edited by Corresponding Member of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Doctor of Philosophy E. Holovakha, Doctor of Social Sciences S. Makeyev) as well as to S. Plokyh's fundamental work "The Russo-Ukrainian War: The Return of History." In particular, the latest study highlights the determination of the Western democratic alliance led by the United States "...to eliminate the Russian threat to peace not only in Ukraine but throughout the world by ensuring Russia's defeat in the current war and reducing its ability to wage war in the future" [Plokyh, 2023: p.269].

The humanitarian crisis and human rights violations in Russia itself have become a decisive factor in the escalation and unleashing of full-scale aggression against the Ukrainian people with the aim of destroying national identity, as it happened before during the tsarist and Soviet periods. Today it is the persistent awareness of the threat to sustainable development and the principles of collective security that encourages European countries to cooperate and confront the military and economic resources used by Russia to expand its interests and change the geopolitical situation in the region.

The purpose of the article. The purpose of the article is to provide a comprehensive study of Russia's aggressive and insidious policy which has been embodied in the unleashing of full-scale military operations throughout Ukraine. The main methods of studying this problem were the comparative historical method and the method of extrapolation. Together with other methods they contributed to a comprehensive analysis of the political relations between the national state administrations during their independent existence in various historical periods and Russian tsarism. The methodological basis of the study was strengthened by identifying key threats to the sustainable development of democracy, outlining important aspects of the crisis shifts that led to full-scale aggression and threaten stability, security and European values, and studying geopolitical factors that influence the process of transformation of the country's modern social development.

Presentation of the main research material. History doesn't know other times when having first appeared on the political scene Ukraine would not have attracted the attention of European states. This attitude was due not only to its strategically important geopolitical position but also to the gradual acquisition of considerable political, economic and cultural weight in the context of the emergence and development of national state associations.

Even during the existence of Kyivan Rus, long before the emergence of the Russian Empire, there were developed trade and economic relations with the countries in the West and the East, powerful military and political alliances were formed, family and dynastic marriage contracts were concluded, etc. The sources and literature of those times provide us with vivid evidence of great respect, emotional admiration and outright sympathy of contemporaries for the Ukrainian people who already played an important role in the development of Europe at that time. Remaining a highly cultured ethnic community, Ukraine in terms of its development was much closer to the foundations of civilization and democracy than Russia. [Minosian, Varypaev , Yurchenko, 2021: p.62]

Later, in the times of the Cossacks which researchers considered a "brave and untamed nation" Ukraine also came into the spotlight of Western attention [Kappeler, 2022: p.63]. The national liberation struggle of the Ukrainian people for the creation of an independent state in the 17th century was an organic continuation of a series of European revolutions that marked the beginning of capitalist relations. In the context of solving complex political tasks of that period, Ukraine found itself under the pressure of external aggression from its northern neighbour which used the powerful human, economic and cultural potential of the Ukrainian people in its own interests. Modern researchers, drawing historical analogies with the current full-scale invasion of Ukrainian lands, note that even then "Moscow uses the protection of the Orthodox in Ukraine as a pretext for war with Poland" [Kappeler, 2022: p77]. Nevertheless, under certain conditions, it was possible to preserve the signs of an independent Ukrainian state in the struggle against Russian tsarism thanks to the support of European allies, in particular the Swedes, and the unbroken spirit of the nation itself..[Kappeler, 2022: p.137-138] .

For several centuries, Ukraine, overcoming numerous difficulties and obstacles, through hard struggles, losses and trials, has been trying to realize the inherent right to exist as an independent state. A copy of Pylyp Orlyk's letter dated in Stockholm on April 30, 1720, points to the insatiable expansionism of the Russian Empire, emphasising the difference between Russia and Ukraine, whose people "yearn for their freedom and only expect to find protection and help to rise up against Russia".[Novak, 2021: p.82].

Considering Ukraine only in the context of adherence to a pro-Russian position, fiercely defending the interests of the empire in relation to the so-called periphery, repressing anyone who demonstrated a distinct Ukrainian identity in the political or cultural sphere [Liber, 2019: p.64], Russia assessed its alleged independence as a temporary anomaly, a sign of undemocracy and the result of intrigue by foreign forces based on narrow nationalism. [Novak, 2021: p.303-304]. Later, continuing the traditions of imperial power, [Bezanson, 2017: p.84-85], the Bolsheviks were not ready to give up control over the whole of Ukraine with its economic and strategic importance [Novak, 2021: p.129], considering their aggressive actions as a sacred mission of liberation from the imperialists.[Johnson, 2022: p. 63]. For example, in the international arena, the "eternal" desire of the Ukrainians and the Belarusians to live in one state was used as a justification for the Soviet annexation of parts of pre-war Poland, Romania and Czechoslovakia [Plokyh, 2019: p.98]. A similar scenario occurred when the modern Russia occupied certain territories of Donetsk and Luhansk regions in 2014.

The West's interest in our country was largely based on the understanding of support for the Ukrainian national movement in the struggle for independence and freedom, because "if Ukraine was made up of its people, then the Ukrainian state had to extend within its borders"

[Snyder, 2021: p.165] as well as the danger of Russian and later Soviet expansion in the context of an unstable political situation in the world. On the other hand, indecision and excessive fears of considering the Ukrainian question separately from the Russian/Soviet state made it much more difficult to establish the Ukrainian people as a real nation with an unconditional right to independent development [Minosian , Varypaev , Yurchenko, 2023: p.95].

In this struggle the Ukrainian people had to rely on the support and assistance of the countries that had freed themselves from the long-term Russian occupation, including Poland and the Baltic states. "In the fight against Russian expansion... we will not be supported by a coalition but only by those nations that, like Poland, and maybe even more are under threat from all great Russia. Therefore, it is a matter of crucial importance for Poland to orientate and oblige Ukraine to the west, i.e. to Poland, and not to the east, i.e. to Russia." [Suleya, 2018: p.278]. In view of Poland's enormous fraternal assistance to Ukraine in overcoming the current Russian aggression, the words of the prominent Polish statesman and statesman Józef Piłsudski about the need to "correct the mistakes of our ancestors by giving our outlying brethren the opportunity to self-determination and governance for their own nation", the opportunity to "win their own will and ensure happiness and prosperity for the fertile land of their homeland" are deeply symbolic. [Suleya, 2018: p.296]

The Anschluss of Austria, the seizure of Czechoslovakia, and the partition of Poland took place with the tacit approval and unwillingness to abandon the policy of appeasement of the aggressors, which were the Soviet Union and Nazi Germany, as well as fascist Italy. [Minosian, Varypaev, 2021: p.199]. Considering the policy of appeasement unacceptable and absolutely senseless from a strategic point of view because all totalitarian regimes should be resisted the prominent British politician Winston Churchill in his address to the House of Commons after the Munich Agreement on September 30, 1938 emphasized: "... we have crossed a terrible historical line, when the balance on the European continent was completely destroyed and now the Western democracy received a terrible ancient sentence: "your capabilities have been weighed in the scales and found weak." And further: "And do not hope this is the end. The reckoning has only just begun. This is only the first sip, the first taste of the bitter glass from which we will drink year after year if we do not restore our mental health and fighting spirit, if we do not rise again to fight for our freedom as we have done since ancient times." [Axelrod, 2022: p.151]. Contemporary Western politicians should keep this in mind when it comes to coordinated and decisive action to overcome Russian aggression against Ukraine and to provide the latter with the opportunity for a future equal partnership in the post-war European space.

The confluence of circumstances that arose from the collapse of the Soviet system in 1991 contributed to the peaceful nature of Ukraine's independence, as the Russian authorities were distracted by their own needs to resolve the complex political processes taking place in that country, but did not guarantee that the northern neighbour would not take a "brotherly interest" in the political future of the Ukrainian people, which eventually happened. Almost immediately, Ukraine faced undisguised Russian hostility to everything that arose in Ukrainian society on national grounds.

This was facilitated by the presence of a variety of pro-Russian parties and organizations in the political space of our country, representation of outspoken apologists for the "Russian world" in the pro-government structures, the presence of agents of the Russian special services, their actual control over the media, and others. At that time, Ukrainian society was at the stage of transition to the

development of a national model of the state, strengthening its priority, filling it with traditions of the national heritage, overcoming Soviet narratives which caused considerable opposition from the conservative part of the population which was in difficult socio-economic conditions of life at the end of the 20-th century and accused the national authorities for this.

Even then, the previously formed "historically justified" claims of the Russian authorities to Ukrainian territories were renewed, as well as slogans about the alleged artificiality of the formation of our state, the accidental and unnatural severance of ties with the "brotherly" Russian people. Later, this was supplemented by demands to resolve existential issues that denied the very possibility of the existence of the Ukrainian nation.

It coincided that Europe was also in a state of rethinking the processes observed in the Eastern European countries, which largely prevented it from taking a closer look at the significant political, economic and cultural potential that Ukraine possessed. There was also a lack of responsible politicians who would be able to free themselves from Russian influence on the formation of a new political reality. The political systems of European states have become the object of targeted influence of Russian resources, agents of influence, and manipulative tools. [Magda, 2017: p.215]. The active interference of Russian politics in the life and activities of Western countries, strong financial support for certain political parties and movements, the presence of "sympathisers" in the pro-government structures - all this not least influenced the preservation of the status quo in relation to Ukraine as an "indigenous" Russian zone of influence with signs of ownership. Later investigations and revelations related to this problem became a real shock for the European political community.

Communication with the West was also significantly hampered by the uncertainty of the Ukrainian authorities regarding the choice of political development paths, the search for "multi-vector", and their excessive expectations of compliance with international treaties on support and guarantees of security, sovereignty and territorial integrity as in the case of the Budapest Memorandum. Remaining in the grip of Soviet stereotypes, Ukrainian society has made very slow progress in resolving issues related to Ukraine's localization in the European space.

The post-war world, which gained its sustainable stability after 1945 and of which Europe remained a part, was largely based on the legal order that had been built by the efforts of the leading democratic countries, newly created international organizations such as the UN and NATO, and the collective awareness of the threat of a new world war, which, if it did happen, would be significantly different from the previous one in the context of the emergence and proliferation of nuclear weapons. The Soviet Union, despite its aggressive militaristic nature, was always forced to come to terms with the new political reality, being unable to compete economically in the field of the latest technologies. In addition, the test of democracy through the victorious actions and successes of Western countries in various spheres of life, the collapse of the colonial system and the strengthening of political independence of Eastern countries seemed to allow for a fixed balance in decision-making in overcoming global problems.

The Russian aggression, which began in 2014 and continued in 2022 with a full-scale invasion of Ukrainian lands, has created completely new realities for the existence of the civilized world. The armed attack on Ukraine has finally undermined the collective security system established after the end of World War II. The weakness and indecision of the international community, which became apparent at the beginning of the twenty-first century during the territorial seizures of Georgia, the annexation of the Crimea and the occupation of a part of Donbas, did not contribute to the adoption of decisions that would prevent the destruction of the existing world order. The bitter experience and important lessons

learned from the policy of appeasement of the aggressor, which was historically observed in the twentieth century, did not become a guarantee of more decisive actions by Western politicians to curb Russian state expansion.

As in the past, fluctuations in European policy were largely due to an overestimation of the existing threat posed by the nuclear power that remains Russia and unjustified expectations from it to strictly comply with international legal norms and rules. In addition, in the current conditions there has been a significant shortage of the most responsible politicians capable of being consistent and convincing in defending basic democratic values.

Through its national resistance in this war, Ukraine has set an example for the entire world of the unity of society around the idea of sovereignty and territorial integrity of the state, preservation of national identity and the priority of the rights and freedoms of every person. Russia's rejection of the European choice of the Ukrainian people, the deliberate destruction of everything related to its cultural and historical heritage, ethnic characteristics have created a situation where the practice of depriving one people (in this case, the Ukrainian people) of its independence and autonomy by another state through forceful intervention has been introduced, which has led to violations of universal human values and international law and, accordingly, has affected the willingness of Western politicians to revise existing international obligations in the context of military and political adventures of the Russian authorities. [Ukrainian Society in the Context of War..., 2022: p.31], returning the West to the historical arena in full force. [Plokyh,2023: p. 286]

Today, we are witnessing an increase in the Western political establishment's sustained interest in the Ukrainian people's resistance to Russian aggression. Ukraine demonstrates a high level of political consciousness destroys the ideology of the "Russian world" and categorically rejects the post-war reconstruction of Ukraine outside NATO and the EU.

The Western democratic alliance, not counting on the probability of fundamental changes in Russian society in the presence of the existing political leadership, demonstrates awareness of the need to break up the Russian empire into separate independent state formations on a national basis. It is making unprecedented efforts to provide comprehensive military, economic, political assistance and support to the Ukrainian people and its state in their efforts to confront and defeat a powerful aggressor, aiming to restore the system of collective security in the world, to affirm the inviolability of the rights and freedoms of all peoples, the rule of democracy and the priority of universal human values. It is important that "Washington and its European allies have managed to develop a common platform united by Russia's aggression and the threat it poses to Europe and the international order" [Plokyh, 2023: p. 286]. It is also absolutely clear that "the war buried Russia's hope of becoming a new global centre in a multipolar world, which Russian politicians and diplomats had dreamed of since the 1990s" [S. Plokyh, 2023: p. 315]. Last but not least, in the new political configuration that is being formed today, which involves the world's leading democracies, Ukraine is seen as a powerful link that will help shape a new European reality free from any existential threats.

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